

Automatic Image Captioning

Sagnik Mukherjee, Toulik Das, and Rupam Patra

Abstract—In the past few years, neural networks have updated tremendously in the area of image classification. With advancement of artificial intelligence and computer vision systems, researchers are also looking for more challenging problems. Among them, image and video captioning is one of the most popular applications to develop more advanced automated computing systems.

In this project, we designed an image captioning system using convolution deep neural networks and recurrent neural networks. We designed an encoder–decoder model based on a recurrent neural network architecture which combines recent developments in CNN architecture, image processing, machine translation using an attention based model, and it can be used to auto-generate captions which describe an image, what is going on in the given image, or it can also be used in videos. The model is trained and tuned to maximize the probability of the target image description given the training image.

We validate the use of attention with state-of-the-art performance on the following benchmark datasets: Flickr8k, Flickr30k, and Microsoft Common Objects in Context (COCO). Our experiments on this dataset show that the deep neural networks implemented throughout the project generate sensible and accurate image descriptions in most of the test cases, and hyperparameter tuning using dropout and number of LSTM layers can successfully reduce the effect of overfitting, i.e., the highest risk in the whole problem. To our knowledge, it is a novel contribution.

Index Terms—Computer Vision, Convolution Neural Network, Recurrent Neural Network, LSTMs, Attention Model, Gated Recurrent Unit, Natural Language Processing, Transfer Learning, Generative Pre-Trained Transform.

I. INTRODUCTION

AUTOMATIC captions generation of an image is a task very close to the scene understanding of real time objects—one of the primary goals of computer vision. Being able to auto-caption and describe the situation of an image using properly formed sentences is a very challenging task, but it can create great impact, for instance by helping people who lost their eyesight understand the real time environment in a better way, while self-driving vehicles can get the real time scenario in a very efficient way. This task is significantly harder, as the generated caption not only describes the real time objects, but it also must express how these objects relate to each other as well as their attributes and the activities they are involved in. Moreover, the visual understanding must be expressed in natural language form or in audio output. So, besides the critical visual understanding, language generation or audio generation is an addition to it.

For our project we used attention based transfer learning techniques which extract features from images using different CNN architectures, combine the features using transfer learning techniques, and generate captions using RNN. Related multimodal annotation resources and background material also informed the original project study [8], [16], [17]. For a

contemporary implementation perspective, TensorFlow’s official image-captioning tutorial provides an end-to-end visual-attention workflow in which extracted image features are passed to a Transformer decoder [19].

A. Motivation

In this section we describe the importance of the problem with respect to real world scenarios. Here are a few of the most important applications where it can be helpful.

- **Self Driving Vehicles:** Self driving systems are one of the biggest challenges, and driving requires many social interactions which are still tough for robots to understand. Much of the self-driving testing done by Google Waymo and the MIT Moral Machine is based on training the car’s software to recognize the real world situations that pop up on the roads [17].
- **Blind People:** We can develop products for blind people. It will guide them while travelling on the roads without the support of anyone else. We can do this by first converting the scene into text and then the text to voice. Both are now famous applications of deep learning.
- **Surveillance Systems:** Using these captioning systems we can develop much more efficient surveillance systems. Not only that, it can be applied to drowsiness detection systems, which can be one of the most trustable inventions in the domain of robotics.
- **Search Engine:** Google Lens can be as good as a Google Search Engine using these captioning techniques efficiently.

Their possibilities are endless; here we mention only a few of them. So we chose this area to work on as our major project.

B. Related Works

Table I reproduces the related-work summary presented in the original report.

II. OBJECTIVE

The project aims at understanding the different parts of long term recurrent convolutional networks. The overview of our contribution is as follows.

- 1) Understanding the different convolution neural network architectures, e.g., AlexNet, VGGNet, GoogLeNet, etc.
- 2) Analyzing the effect of the CNN component by replacing it with different deep architectures.
- 3) Designing neural machine translation models for developing encoder–decoder networks for image captioning, e.g., NMT using Seq2Seq and Bahdanau Attention.
- 4) Finally, using all these to develop a caption generation system with the Common Objects in Context dataset.

TABLE I
RELATED WORKS CONSIDERED IN THE ORIGINAL REPORT.

Prior Work	Source
Captioning methods based on RNN, Seq2Seq models, and machine translation	Bahdanau, Dzmitry, machine translation by jointly learning, September 2014 [1]; Sutskever, Ilya, Vinyals, Oriol, and Le, Quoc VV, NIPS, pp. 3104–3112, 2014 [2]
Multimodal log-bilinear model that was biased by features from the image	Kiros, Ryan, Salahutdinov, International Conference on Machine Learning, pp. 595–603, 2014a [3]
Unifying visual-semantic embeddings with multimodal neural language models	arXiv:1411.2539, November 2014b [4]
Topic-Oriented Image Captioning Based on Order-Embedding	IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, vol. 28, no. 6, June 2019 [5]
Retrieval Topic Recurrent Memory Network for Remote Sensing Image Captioning	IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing, February 2020 [6]
Re-Caption: Saliency-Enhanced Image Captioning Through Two-Phase Learning	IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, vol. 29, 2019–July 2020 [7]

III. PROBLEM OVERVIEW

In this project, we want to build a deep learning model that can generate captions in English language which can describe an RGB image:

$$S = f(J) \quad (1)$$

where J is the given RGB image and S is the generated sentence in English, and f is the function that generates the sentence, i.e., our objective to design.

We are using the Microsoft Common Objects in Context dataset. It contains 330K images and among them over 220K images are labeled. Each image has at least five captions for training. It also has 1.5 million object instances and more than 80 object categories.

IV. TOOLS AND TECHNOLOGY USED

- 1) Python 3.7
- 2) OpenCV 2
- 3) TensorFlow 2.0
- 4) NLTK 3.5
- 5) Scikit-Learn 0.23
- 6) Google Colab
- 7) Jupyter Notebook and Python IDLE

V. SOLVING METHOD

A. Feature Extraction

For image captioning, long term recurrent convolutional network maximizes the probability of accurate caption generation of a given image:

$$\theta^* = \arg \max_{\theta} \sum_{(J,S)} \log p(S | J; \theta) \quad (2)$$

Here θ is the parameters of our model, J is the given image, and S is the generated caption. Let the length of the caption be N ; the method applies the chain rule on the model joint probability over S_0, \dots, S_N :

$$\log p(S | J) = \sum_{t=0}^N \log p(S_t | J, S_0, \dots, S_{t-1}) \quad (3)$$

Here θ is dropped for convenience, and the word at step t is represented by S_t .

The model is designed in two parts. In the first part, convolution neural network extracts the features of a given image, i.e., maps the fixed length visual features to the RGB image. Extracted embedded features of that image are used as an input to the recurrent neural network:

$$v = W_v(\text{CNN}(J)) \quad (4)$$

Here v is the extracted features used as an input to the RNN, and W_v is the feature embedding.

B. Caption Generation

In this project we used a powerful variant on recurrent neural networks called Long Short Term Memory unit. In the RNN, one-hot key vector represents each word. S_0 and S_N are the start and stop words. W_s is the word embedding parameter:

$$x_t = W_s S_t, \quad t \in \{0, \dots, N-1\} \quad (5)$$

Images and words are mapped with each other to the same vector space in this way. After the processing of recurrent neural networks to predict the word in real time, the features (v, x_t, h_t) are decoded into a probability:

$$p_{t+1} = \text{LSTM}(v, x_t, h_t), \quad t \in \{0, \dots, N-1\} \quad (6)$$

VI. CNN ARCHITECTURE

Here we discuss different deep learning architectures developed in 2012–2016, leading to a boosted accuracy and performance. A few of them are as follows.

- ResNet
- SqueezeNet
- Inception v3

Fig. 1. Feature extraction using CNN.

Figure 6. Image feature being mapped to the LSTM Network

Fig. 2. Image Features mapped to the LSTM Network.

- VGG Net
- AlexNet
- GoogleNet

After testing with different models, in this project we specifically used Inception v3 architecture.

A. ResNet

As deep learning networks take much time to train and face issues of overfitting, a team of Microsoft introduced ResNet architecture which is also called residual learning framework. ResNet is also called residual mapping, as it helps to combat this issue. Residual network explicitly helps neural layers to fit a residual mapping. The basic building blocks of the network are as follows.

Fig. 3. Building Block Of ResNet.

Many problems can be solved and accuracy can be optimized by ResNet. The performance of the network depends on the depths of the neural layers. The figure below presents the difference between a normal 34-layer neural network, a 34-layer residual neural network, and VGG network architectures.

B. VGG 16

VGG16 is a Convolutional Neural Network model preferred by Simonyan and Zisserman from the University of Oxford in the paper “Very Deep Convolutional Networks for Large-Scale Image Recognition.” This model reached 92.7% top-5 test accuracy in ImageNet, with over 14 million images close to 1000 classes. It is the famous CNN model submitted to ILSVRC-2014. It makes the upgrade over AlexNet by restoring large kernel-sized filters with multiple 3×3 kernel-sized filters one after another. VGG16 is trained using NVIDIA Titan Black GPU for a week.

C. Inception V3

Inception v3 optimizes computational power by improving earlier Inception architectures. Compared to VGGNet, Inception Networks have provided more computationally efficient models, in terms of the number of parameters generated by the network as well as the economical cost incurred. Any changes made to an Inception Network require developments so that the computational advantages are not lost. In this way, due to the uncertainty of the new network’s efficiency, the adaptation of an Inception network for different use cases turns out to be a problem. In an Inception v3 model, several techniques for optimizing the network have been suggested to loosen the constraints for easier model adaptation. The techniques include performing factorized convolutions, followed by regularization, dimension reduction, and finally parallelized computations [15].

Finally, after merging all the factors we get the following architecture structure.

D. CNN Encoder

In this project, convolution neural network maps an image to visual feature vectors. The most used layers in convolution neural networks are convolution, pooling, and fully-connected layers. Rectified Linear Unit is used as the nonlinear activation

Fig. 4. Comparison of ResNet-34, VGG-19 and 34-layer Neural Network.

Fig. 5. VGG 16 Architecture.

Fig. 6. Inception v3 layers.

function. The ReLU is faster than the tanh or sigmoid function. Dropout layer is used to get rid of overfitting.

So, here we used a neural machine translation method based on CNN encoder network using an attention model. Like common statistical machine translation, the neural-network-based machine translation used to develop a single neural network can be tuned and optimized to get the maximum translation performance. As the word attention says, the training and optimization are done by taking a few features as exclusive or important, i.e., giving them much more priority in the model.

The encoder components consist of a stack of encoders, each of them broken into two sublayers and having identical structures.

The encoding task is performed in the bottom layer of the encoder. The abstraction relatable to these encoders is that they get a list of feature vectors, in general each of size 512.

In the architecture of the encoder, each sublayer has a residual connection around the neural layer and is followed by a layer-normalization step. This applies to both the self-attention and feed-forward sublayers. There are multiple types

Fig. 7. Inception V3 Architecture.

Fig. 8. Attention Encoder Layer.

of attention layer; among them we used Bahdanau attention method.

VII. RNN ARCHITECTURE

With the attention technique, in the first step the RGB image is divided into n parts, then each of those parts is represented by computing the vectors h_1, \dots, h_n through convolution neural networks. When the RNN generates new words, the attention method focuses on a few relevant parts of the image for that decoder and uses a few specific parts of that image.

For image classification tasks we can recognize the object of a classic model given for testing with a new layer of attention model. But the situation becomes challenging when one wants to predict the new word of the caption. If our target is to predict words, then the hidden layers of LSTM networks become important. Then we choose the relevant parts of the RGB image by using the context. Attention layer gets these inputs and gives the relevant parts of the image as an output. Then it is used as an input to LSTM. The LSTM layer processes those inputs, predicts new words, and returns a new hidden state.

There are two types of attention model: global attention model or Luong's attention, i.e., attention is applied on all source positions; and local attention or Bahdanau attention, i.e., attention is applied on a few specific points.

These attention methods differ from each other in the way they compute the context vector C_t . Here we used the local attention method, or Bahdanau attention [1]. The original

project report also consulted public explanatory resources on sequence-to-sequence learning, attention, and encoder-decoder networks [9], [11]–[14].

$$f_{ATT} = V_{attn}^T \tanh(U_{attn}h_j + W_{attn}S_t) \quad (7)$$

where $V_{attn}^T \in \mathbb{R}^d$, $U_{attn} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$, $W_{attn} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$, $S_{t-1} \in \mathbb{R}^d$, and $h_j \in \mathbb{R}^d$.

For local attention and global attention with general score we write

$$e_j^t = f_{ATT}(S_{t-1}, h_j) \quad (8)$$

Here e_j^t represents, at every time-step of decoder, how important the j th pixel location in the input image is. S_{t-1} says the previous state of decoder, and h_j presents the state of encoder.

Finally, using softmax we get the probability distribution,

$$\alpha_j^t = \text{Softmax}(e_j^t) = \frac{\exp(e_j^t)}{\sum_{k=1}^T \exp(e_k^t)} \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^T \alpha_j^t = 1, \quad \alpha_j^t \geq 0 \quad (10)$$

Now we know the input and need to feed a weighted sum combination of input to decoder and generate a context vector C_t ,

$$C_t = \sum_{j=1}^T \alpha_j^t h_j \quad (11)$$

Finally we can get the output of the present state of decoder,

$$S_t = \text{RNN}(S_{t-1}, e(\hat{y}_{t-1}), C_t) \quad (12)$$

where S_t is the present state of decoder, S_{t-1} is the previous state of decoder (previous predicted caption), $e(\hat{y}_{t-1})$ is the previous predicted word embedding, and C_t is the context vector or weighted sum of inputs.

Visualization of decoder of the Bahdanau Attention model is as follows.

The RNN decoder model designed an attention system using a gated recurrent unit or GRU, a word embedding as an

Fig. 9. Vector Flow In Encoder Layer.

Fig. 10. Encoder layer visualization.

input, and two fully connected layer operations. So complete representation of encoder–decoder network is as follows.

VIII. PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

There are a lot of open source image datasets available for image processing and segmentation, such as Flickr datasets, Flickr30k, MS COCO, and VizWiz-Captions. Here in the core implementation described in the original project we used the MS COCO dataset. The specification of this dataset is as follows.

- 1) 300k images, out of them 200k labeled.
- 2) More than 1.5 million object instances.
- 3) More than 80 object categories in the whole dataset.
- 4) In each image there are five captions.

In addition to MS COCO, accessibility-oriented image-captioning benchmarks such as VizWiz-Captions are highly relevant to this problem setting. The VizWiz-Captions dataset consists of 39,181 images taken by people who are blind, and each image is paired with five captions, making it a valuable dataset resource for assistive-captioning evaluation and future extension of this work [20].

To make the whole process faster we used a subset of the dataset which contains 30k–60k images and their captions for training the model.

First of all, the images are converted to the format expected by the Inception v3 architecture.

- 1) Images resized into 299×299 .
- 2) Preprocess the images to normalize them so that they are converted into pixels in range -1 to 1 , which is the expected format of Inception v3.

Next we create a `tf.keras` model using the output layer ($8 \times 8 \times 2048$) of the last CNN layer of Inception v3 architecture. As we used the attention method, that is why we used the last layer. During this training process, initializing this model can cause bottleneck issues, so we perform this initialization previously.

Next we preprocess captions in the following way.

- 1) Tokenize the captions so that a vocabulary of different unique words is learned from the captions.
- 2) To make the process faster, limit the vocabulary size to 5k words.
- 3) Perform word-to-index and index-to-word mapping.
- 4) Pad all the sequences to the same length.

Next we developed encoder–decoder architecture with an attention model using the *Show, Attend and Tell* paper.

- 1) Extract RGB image features from the last convolution layer of Inception V3, which gives a vector of shape $8 \times 8 \times 2048$.
- 2) Then squash that vector shape into 64×2048 .
- 3) Then this vector is passed through convolution neural encoder, i.e., it consists of a single fully connected layer.
- 4) Then the RNN based decoder attends over the image to predict the next word.

Next we divided the image dataset and captions into train–test splits in 80–20 and, as per our system capability, we chose batch size, buffer size, embedding dimension, vocabulary size, and feature shapes.

Finally we perform the training as follows.

- 1) The features extracted from Inception v3 and dumped in `.numpy` files are passed through the CNN encoder.
- 2) Then the CNN encoder’s outputs, hidden states, and the start tokens from the caption, i.e., decoder inputs, are passed to the RNN decoder.
- 3) The RNN decoder returns the hidden states and the predictions of captions.

Fig. 11. Representation of Attention Model.

Fig. 12. Comparison of Global and local attention model.

Fig. 13. Bahdanau Attention model.

- 4) The hidden states are again passed through the model and predicted values are used to calculate the loss and tune them.
- 5) After that, to decide the next input in the decoder we used teacher forcing technique.
- 6) The final task is to calculate the gradients, apply these to optimizer, and backpropagate.

The implementation study in the original project also consulted public resources on sequence-to-sequence learning, autoencoders, attention mechanisms, encoder–decoder models,

and Inception v3 [9]–[15], as well as NVIDIA cuTENSOR documentation [18].

IX. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Results

The original report presented five representative qualitative results, reproduced here as Figs. 26–30.

Fig. 14. Visualization of RNN Decoder.

Fig. 15. Architecture of transformer with a encoder decoder layer.

```
def load_image(image_path):
    img = tf.io.read_file(image_path)
    img = tf.image.decode_jpeg(img, channels=3)
    img = tf.image.resize(img, (299, 299))
    img = tf.keras.applications.inception_v3.preprocess_input(img)
    return img, image_path
```

Fig. 16. Image Processing for Inception v3.

```
image_model = tf.keras.applications.InceptionV3(include_top=False,
                                              weights='imagenet')
new_input = image_model.input
hidden_layer = image_model.layers[-1].output

image_features_extract_model = tf.keras.Model(new_input, hidden_layer)
```

Fig. 17. Initializing Inception v3.

conv2d_95 (Conv2D)	(None, None, None, 3 655360)	size0[0][0]
batch_normalization_87 (BatchNorm)	(None, None, None, 3 1152)	conv2d_97[0][0]
batch_normalization_88 (BatchNorm)	(None, None, None, 3 1152)	conv2d_98[0][0]
batch_normalization_91 (BatchNorm)	(None, None, None, 3 1152)	conv2d_91[0][0]
batch_normalization_92 (BatchNorm)	(None, None, None, 3 1152)	conv2d_92[0][0]
conv2d_93 (Conv2D)	(None, None, None, 1 393216)	average_pooling2d_1[0][0]
batch_normalization_85 (BatchNorm)	(None, None, None, 3 960)	conv2d_81[0][0]
activation_87 (Activation)	(None, None, None, 3 0)	batch_normalization_87[0][0]
activation_88 (Activation)	(None, None, None, 3 0)	batch_normalization_88[0][0]
activation_91 (Activation)	(None, None, None, 3 0)	batch_normalization_91[0][0]
activation_92 (Activation)	(None, None, None, 3 0)	batch_normalization_92[0][0]
batch_normalization_93 (BatchNorm)	(None, None, None, 1 576)	conv2d_93[0][0]
activation_95 (Activation)	(None, None, None, 3 0)	batch_normalization_95[0][0]
size0_1 (Concatenate)	(None, None, None, 7 0)	activation_91[0][0]
concatenate_1 (Concatenate)	(None, None, None, 7 0)	activation_92[0][0]
activation_93 (Activation)	(None, None, None, 1 0)	batch_normalization_93[0][0]
size0[0] (Concatenate)	(None, None, None, 2 0)	activation_87[0][0]
		size0_1[0][0]
		concatenate_1[0][0]
		activation_93[0][0]
Total params: 21,003,784		
Trainable params: 21,768,352		
Non-trainable params: 24,432		

Fig. 18. Inception V3 architecture last few layers summary.

```
[14] # Find the maximum length of any caption in our dataset
def calc_max_length(tensor):
    return max(len(t) for t in tensor)

[15] # Choose the top 5000 words from the vocabulary
top_k = 5000
tokenizer = tf.keras.preprocessing.text.Tokenizer(num_words=top_k,
                                                  oov_token='<unk>',
                                                  filters='!#$%&()*+,-./:;<=>[\\]^_`{|}~ ')

tokenizer.fit_on_texts(train_captions)
train_seqs = tokenizer.texts_to_sequences(train_captions)

[16] tokenizer.word_index['<pad>'] = 0
tokenizer.index_word[0] = '<pad>'

[17] # Create the tokenized vectors
train_seqs = tokenizer.texts_to_sequences(train_captions)

[18] # Pad each vector to the max_length of the captions
# If you do not provide a max_length value, pad_sequences calculates it automatically
cap_vector = tf.keras.preprocessing.sequence.pad_sequences(train_seqs, padding='post')

[19] # Calculates the max_length, which is used to store the attention weights
max_length = calc_max_length(train_seqs)
```

Fig. 19. Caption Processing.

```
[26] class CNN_Encoder(tf.keras.Model):
    # Since you have already extracted the features and dumped it using pickle
    # This encoder passes those features through a Fully connected layer
    def __init__(self, embedding_dim):
        super(CNN_Encoder, self).__init__()
        # shape after fc == (batch_size, 64, embedding_dim)
        self.fc = tf.keras.layers.Dense(embedding_dim)

    def call(self, x):
        x = self.fc(x)
        x = tf.nn.relu(x)
        return x
```

Fig. 20. CNN Encoder.

```
class BahdanauAttention(tf.keras.Model):
    def __init__(self, units):
        super(BahdanauAttention, self).__init__()
        self.W1 = tf.keras.layers.Dense(units)
        self.W2 = tf.keras.layers.Dense(units)
        self.V = tf.keras.layers.Dense(1)

    def call(self, features, hidden):
        # features (CNN_encoder output) shape == (batch_size, 64, embedding_dim)
        # hidden shape == (batch_size, hidden_size)
        # hidden_with_time_axis shape == (batch_size, 1, hidden_size)
        hidden_with_time_axis = tf.expand_dims(hidden, 1)

        # attention_hidden_layer shape == (batch_size, 64, units)
        attention_hidden_layer = (tf.nn.tanh(self.W1(features) +
                                             self.W2(hidden_with_time_axis)))

        # score shape == (batch_size, 64, 1)
        # This gives you an unnormalized score for each image feature.
        score = self.V(attention_hidden_layer)

        # attention_weights shape == (batch_size, 64, 1)
        attention_weights = tf.nn.softmax(score, axis=-1)

        # context_vector shape after sum == (batch_size, hidden_size)
        context_vector = attention_weights * features
        context_vector = tf.reduce_sum(context_vector, axis=-1)

        return context_vector, attention_weights
```

Fig. 21. Local attention model.

```

class RNN_Decoder(tf.keras.Model):
    def __init__(self, embedding_dim, units, vocab_size):
        super(RNN_Decoder, self).__init__()
        self.units = units

        self.embedding = tf.keras.layers.Embedding(vocab_size, embedding_dim)
        self.gru = tf.keras.layers.GRU(self.units,
                                       return_sequences=True,
                                       return_state=True,
                                       recurrent_initializer='glorot_uniform')

        self.fc1 = tf.keras.layers.Dense(self.units)
        self.fc2 = tf.keras.layers.Dense(vocab_size)

        self.attention = BahdanauAttention(self.units)

    def call(self, x, features, hidden):
        # defining attention as a separate model
        context_vector, attention_weights = self.attention(features, hidden)

        # x shape after passing through embedding == (batch_size, 1, embedding_dim)
        x = self.embedding(x)

        # x shape after concatenation == (batch_size, 1, embedding_dim + hidden_size)
        x = tf.concat([tf.expand_dims(context_vector, 1), x], axis=-1)

        # passing the concatenated vector to the GRU
        output, state = self.gru(x)

        # shape == (batch_size, max_length, hidden_size)
        x = self.fc1(output)

        # x shape == (batch_size * max_length, hidden_size)
        x = tf.reshape(x, [-1, x.shape[-1]])

        # output shape == (batch_size * max_length, vocab)
        x = self.fc2(x)

        return x, state, attention_weights

    def reset_state(self, batch_size):
        return tf.zeros((batch_size, self.units))

```

Fig. 22. RNN Decoder.

Fig. 26. Result 1.

```

# As per our system's configuration
BATCH_SIZE = 64
BUFFER_SIZE = 1000
embedding_dim = 256
units = 512
vocab_size = top_k + 1
num_steps = len(img_name_train) // BATCH_SIZE
# Shape of the vector extracted from InceptionV3 is (64, 2048)
# These two variables represent that vector shape
features_shape = 2048
attention_features_shape = 64

# Load the numpy files
def map_func(img_name, cap):
    img_tensor = np.load(img_name.decode('utf-8')+'.npy')
    return img_tensor, cap

dataset = tf.data.Dataset.from_tensor_slices((img_name_train, cap_train))

# Use map to load the numpy files in parallel
dataset = dataset.map(lambda item1, item2: tf.numpy_function(
    map_func, [item1, item2], [tf.float32, tf.int32]),
    num_parallel_calls=tf.data.experimental.AUTOTUNE)

# Shuffle and batch
dataset = dataset.shuffle(BUFFER_SIZE).batch(BATCH_SIZE)
dataset = dataset.prefetch(buffer_size=tf.data.experimental.AUTOTUNE)

```

Fig. 23. Dataset training configuration.

Fig. 27. Result 2.

```

@tf.function
def train_step(img_tensor, target):
    loss = 0

    # initializing the hidden state for each batch
    # because the captions are not related from image to image
    hidden = decoder.reset_state(batch_size=target.shape[0])

    dec_input = tf.expand_dims([tokenizer.word_index['<start>']] * target.shape[0], 1)

    with tf.GradientTape() as tape:
        features = encoder(img_tensor)

        for i in range(1, target.shape[1]):
            # passing the features through the decoder
            predictions, hidden, _ = decoder(dec_input, features, hidden)

            loss += loss_function(target[:, i], predictions)

            # using teacher forcing
            dec_input = tf.expand_dims(target[:, i], 1)

    total_loss = (loss / int(target.shape[1]))

    trainable_variables = encoder.trainable_variables + decoder.trainable_variables
    gradients = tape.gradient(loss, trainable_variables)
    optimizer.apply_gradients(zip(gradients, trainable_variables))

    return loss, total_loss

```

Fig. 24. Model Training.

Fig. 28. Result 3.

```

plt.plot(loss_plot)
plt.xlabel('Epochs')
plt.ylabel('Loss')
plt.title('Loss Plot')
plt.show()

```


Fig. 25. Loss Function of the Trained Model(Epoch 20).

Fig. 29. Result 4.

Fig. 30. Result 5.

B. Future Scope

For future work of this project we can consider the following improvements.

- 1) A real time image is always packed with rich contents. We can develop such models which can generate the natural text corresponding to multiple major objects by categorizing them by their importance in that respective situation, instead of considering one major object in the image.
- 2) The model can be improved in such a way that it can handle multiple languages at once and generate multi-language outputs.
- 3) Verifying the generated results of natural language processing systems is a difficult task. One of the better ways to evaluate the generated text is subjective tests by linguists, but that is hard to achieve. So for that, evaluation indicators must be tuned and optimized to align them with human level assessment.
- 4) The models developed till now suffer from lack of compositionality and naturalness as their text generation is based on previous words and image features. So we can improve that.
- 5) Last but not least, we can improve the model training time of the RNN model which takes long hours.
- 6) A further extension is to benchmark the present system on accessibility-focused datasets such as VizWiz-Captions and to compare the current RNN-based pipeline against newer Transformer-oriented implementations of the kind illustrated in TensorFlow's official tutorial [19], [20].

C. Challenges

The whole process is full of challenges; among them we list out a few major challenges we faced.

- 1) First of all, we faced challenges during extracting different features from the image and mapping them with proper natural language. As the dataset is full of co-occurrence of some objects, in a few images the scene is very hazy. In that case, neural networks cannot perform that much great. For example, in a night cityscape full of lights, machines may predict the day.

- 2) The second challenge is the dataset bias impacting current captioning systems. The trained models overfit to the common objects that co-occur in a common context (e.g., bed and bedroom), which leads to a problem where such systems struggle to generalize to scenes where the same objects appear in unseen contexts (e.g., bed and forest).
- 3) The third challenge is in the evaluation of the quality of generated captions. Using automated metrics, though partially helpful, is still unsatisfactory since they do not take the image into account.

X. CONCLUSION

In this whole project we used all features of image captioning. We discussed different model frameworks designed in the last few years to solve such kinds of image segmentation, detection, and feature extraction problems. We kept our focus on the algorithmic essence of different attention mechanisms, and after testing various aspects summarized the algorithms of attention and how they are applied. We also summarized the large dataset specifications and different evaluation criteria commonly used in real practice.

XI. INDIVIDUAL CONTRIBUTIONS

The team consisted of three members and each one of them contributed well on their part. The efficiency of the team is surely reflected in the work showcased above.

A. Abstract

In this project, we designed an image captioning system using convolution deep neural networks and recurrent neural networks. We designed an encoder–decoder model based on a recurrent neural network architecture.

B. Individual Contribution and Findings

Sagnik Mukherjee (CSCE, 1729215): Worked on different convolution neural network models. The start included study and construction of the renowned research papers and getting the idea as to how to implement the project in terms of documentation and writing the research paper. Analysis of the

research papers was done and their outcomes are compared. Project planning and methodology lie under the work exhibited.

Toulik Das (CSCE, 1729231): Worked on different transfer learning and attention models. Had done research work based on the topics relevant to the project and found the papers holding much importance for the project. Equal contribution in writing the research paper, which was an ongoing work as of then. Helped with the documentation part, basis classifiers and their working. Project planning and methodology lie under the work exhibited.

Rupam Patra (CSCE, 1729237): Worked on different data visualization tools and text preprocessing stage. He also worked on convolution neural network models. Had equal contribution in study of the research papers. Worked out with the code to implement the CNN model. Project planning and methodology lie under the work exhibited.

C. Individual Contribution to Project Report Preparation

Sagnik Mukherjee (CSCE, 1729215): Contributed to documenting convolution neural network models and, along with that, prepared diagrams used in the project report.

Toulik Das (CSCE, 1729231): In this project report, contributed on documenting attention based models and encoder-decoder architecture and, along with that, helped to prepare the introduction, abstract, and objective of the project report.

Rupam Patra (CSCE, 1729237): Documented data exploration and caption preprocessing parts of the project, and along with that helped to collect references from different sources and fix various issues on the overall report.

Author identifiers: Sagnik Mukherjee ORCID: 0009-0002-4111-6299. Prof. Rajat Kumar Behera ORCID: 0009-0007-9201-4846.

HONORS AND RECOGNITION

The paper was graded “O” (Outstanding), the highest grade awarded for the project evaluation, and it was selected for the regional expo.

SCHOLARLY RECORD

This manuscript is an academically faithful IEEE-compliant version prepared for the year 2023 of the original KIIT major project paper *Automatic Image Captioning*. The source report was completed during the academic year 2020–2021 and submitted in November 2020. The original university submission is available at researchgate.net/publication/346715700_Automatic_Image_Captioning. The original authors, cited sources, diagrams, table content, and figure assets have been retained as faithfully as possible while adapting the layout to IEEE manuscript conventions.

Data availability: The archived manuscript record and associated deposited materials for this paper are available via Zenodo at DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20039652.

GitHub repository: github.com/sagnikai/Automatic-Image-Captioning.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We are extremely obliged to Prof. Rajat Kumar Behera for his expert guidance in this project and encouragement throughout to see this project’s objective, in development phase and flow of this project since its commencement to its completion. The work is a team effort, minus which the completion of this project was not possible.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bahdanau, Dzmitry, “machine translation by jointly learning to align and translate,” arXiv:1409.0473, Sep. 2014.
- [2] Sutskever, Ilya, Vinyals, Oriol, and Le, Quoc VV, “NIPS,” pp. 3104–3112, 2014.
- [3] Kiros, Ryan, Salakhutdinov, Ruslan, and Zemel, Richard, “International Conference on Machine Learning,” pp. 595–603, 2014a.
- [4] “Unifying visual-semantic embeddings with multimodal neural language models,” arXiv:1411.2539, Nov. 2014b.
- [5] “Topic-Oriented Image Captioning Based on Order-Embedding,” *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 28, no. 6, Jun. 2019.
- [6] “Retrieval Topic Recurrent Memory Network for Remote Sensing Image Captioning,” *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, Feb. 2020.
- [7] “Re-Caption: Saliency-Enhanced Image Captioning Through Two-Phase Learning,” *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 29, 2019–Jul. 2020.
- [8] A. Torabi, C. Pal, H. Larochelle, and A. Courville, “Using descriptive video services to create a large data source for video annotation research,” arXiv preprint arXiv:1503.01070, 2015.
- [9] Keras Blog, “A ten-minute introduction to sequence-to-sequence learning in Keras.”
- [10] Keras Blog, “Building autoencoders in Keras.”
- [11] Towards Data Science, “Attention networks.”
- [12] Towards Data Science, “Intuitive understanding of attention mechanism in deep learning.”
- [13] Machine Learning Mastery, “Encoder-decoder recurrent neural network models for neural machine translation.”
- [14] G. Karmakar, Medium, “Learning phrase representation using RNN encoder-decoder for machine translation.”
- [15] Google Cloud, “Inception v3 advanced.”
- [16] Testsigma Blog, “Natural language processing (NLP)-based test automation.”
- [17] Towards Data Science, “How do self-driving cars see?”
- [18] NVIDIA, “cuTENSOR 1.2.2 documentation.”
- [19] TensorFlow, “Image captioning with visual attention.”
- [20] VizWiz, “Image captioning: VizWiz-Captions task and dataset.”